

Synthesis of di(4-chlorophenyl)carbazone and its acidity with bivalent metal ions in solution

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Stability constants of the complexes of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} with di(4-chlorophenyl)carbazone (DPCIPC) have been determined pH-metrically in 50% (v/v) aqueous-dioxan at an ionic strength of 0.1 M NaClO₄ at different temperatures. The method of Bjerrum and Calvin, as modified by Irving and Rossotti, has been used to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL. The order of stability constants is found to be : Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Cd^{II} < Ni^{II} = Zn^{II} < Cu^{II}. Thermodynamic parameters have also been calculated.

In view of the biochemical¹ and analytical² importance of DPC (diphenylcarbazone) and its derivatives, it was thought worthwhile to synthesize and study the solution stabilities of the metal chelates of di(4-chlorophenyl)carbazone (DPCIPC) in 50% aqueous dioxan medium at different temperatures. The study includes evaluating thermodynamic parameters and establishing the relationship between log K_1 and atomic numbers, ionization potentials and electronegativities of the metal ions.

Results and discussion

The formation curve of DPCIPC is found to be a single wave extending from 0 to 1 at 25° and the slope of the plot of $\bar{n}_A/(1-\bar{n}_A)$ versus pH is 0.96 – both of which indicate the presence of only one ionisable proton and hence the ligand is monobasic. The observed p*K*_a value is determined from the intercept of the linear plot is found to be 8.83, which is less than that of parent DPC (9.26). This is due to the electron-withdrawing inductive effect (-I) of the Cl group at the *para*-position. On the contrary, the lower value of acid dissociation constant of the ligand compared to its *meta*-chloro derivatives (p*K*_a 8.70)³ reveals that the introduction of Cl atom at the *para* position of the phenyl ring decreases the acid strength of the ligand. Because, the effect of chloro group diminishes the electron-withdrawing inductive effect with increasing separation between the substituent and the ionizable proton. The p*K*_a value of the ligand can also be evaluated using the Hammett relation :

$$\log K = \log K_0 + \rho\sigma$$

Siddalingaiah⁴ determined the value of ρ for the diphenylcarbazone systems in 50% (v/v) aqueous-dioxan

as 2.32. Substituting the value of $\sigma_{p-Cl} = 0.277$ in the above expression⁵, the value of p*K*_a for DPCIPC comes out to be 8.73, which is in good agreement with the experimental value of 8.83.

Table 1. Stability constants of bivalent metal complexes of di(4-chlorophenyl)carbazone (DPCIPC) at different temperatures ($\mu = 0.1 M NaClO_4$) in 50% dioxan-water medium

System	Stability constants	25°	35°	45°
DPCIPC	log K_1^H	8.83	8.78	8.76
Cu ^{II} -DPCIPC	log K_1	9.70	8.76	8.00
	log K_2	9.60	8.47	7.85
	log β_2	19.30	17.23	15.85
Ni ^{II} -DPCIPC	log K_1	6.75	6.48	6.22
	log K_2	6.30	5.71	5.50
	log β_2	13.05	12.19	11.72
Zn ^{II} -DPCIPC	log K_1	6.65	6.44	6.42
	log K_2	6.45	5.96	5.92
	log β_2	13.05	12.40	12.34
Co ^{II} -DPCIPC	log K_1	5.48	5.34	5.18
	log K_2	5.25	5.18	5.06
	log β_2	10.73	10.52	10.24
Cd ^{II} -DPCIPC	log K_1	6.31	6.20	6.14
	log K_2	5.80	5.78	5.66
	log β_2	12.11	11.98	11.80
Mn ^{II} -DPCIPC	log K_1	4.44	4.23	4.11
	log K_2	4.20	4.05	3.98
	log β_2	8.64	8.28	8.09

In general, for a given metal ion, if log K_1 is greater than log K_2 and the difference between them is large, then considerable steric hindrance would be expected during the addition of second ligand molecule. However, the data given in Table 1 shows that the difference in the log K_1 and log K_2

values is small and the ratio of $\log K_1/K_2$ is positive in all the cases indicating that there is no steric hindrance to the addition of second ligand molecule and the tendencies for the formation of complex species ML_2 and ML^+ are almost equal. Further, the maximum values obtained for \bar{n} are < 2 confirming 1 : 2 metal-ligand stoichiometry.

The Table 1 summarizes the formation constants of metal DPCIPC systems at 25, 35 and 45°. The order of overall formation constants investigated is as follows : $Cu^{II} > Ni^{II} > Zn^{II} > Cd^{II} > Co^{II} > Mn^{II}$. This order is in agreement with the order as determined by Mellor and Maley and Irving and Williams⁶. The additional high stability of the Cu^{II} complex may be attributed to the unique electronic configuration ($3d^9$) of Cu^{II} which is capable of deriving additional stabilization due to Jahn Teller distortion. Our studies reveal that Ca^{II} , Ba^{II} , Sr^{II} and Mg^{II} form very weak complexes and hence are not included in the Table 1.

The estimated thermodynamic parameters relating to the complex formation reactions are given in the Table 2. The negative values of ΔG° indicate that the complexation reactions are spontaneous and metal chelates are thermodynamically stable. Negative values of ΔH° indicate that the metal ligand bonds are fairly strong and complexation reactions are exothermic in nature. Large value of $-\Delta H^\circ$ associated with Cu^{II} indicates the high covalent character. In the cases of Cd^{II} and Co^{II} complexes, the ΔS° values are positive and show that the complexation processes are thermodynamically favourable. However, the negative ΔS° values observed in other complexes, show that the loss of entropy during the formation of complexes which are more polar than the reactants and hence strongly solvated.

Table 2. Thermodynamic parameters of bivalent metal complexes with di(4-chlorophenyl)carbazone (DPCIPC) at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ ($\mu = 1.1 M NaClO_4 + HClO_4$)

Metal ion	$-\Delta G^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta H^\circ$ kcal mol ⁻¹	ΔS° e.u.
Cu^{II}	13.26	38.96	-86.20
Ni^{II}	9.23	13.75	-15.16
Zn^{II}	9.09	10.31	-4.09
Co^{II}	7.49	6.88	2.05
Cd^{II}	8.62	4.58	13.55
Mn^{II}	6.07	8.02	-6.54

Experimental

¹H NMR spectra ($CDCl_3$) were recorded on a Varian XI (300 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as an internal reference (chemical shift in δ , ppm), EI mass spectra were recorded on an AEI MS30 instrument equipped with an MSS system and IR spectra on a Perkin-Elmer 1430 spectrophotometer. A Systronics 335 pH-meter with glass and saturated calomel electrodes assembly was used.

Synthesis of ligand involved the following three steps :

4-Chlorophenylhydrazine (1) : 4-Chlorophenylhydrazine hydrochloride⁷ dissolved in hot water and treated with NaOH solution (10%) maintaining the temperature below 15°. The resulting pale yellow hydrazine was extracted with diethyl ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4) and concentrated to yield crystals of 4-chlorophenylhydrazine and dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_5 for 12 h, m.p. 90°.

Di(4-chlorophenyl)carbazide (2) : Compound 1 (0.08 mol) was heated with urea (0.04 mol) in an oil-bath at 140–155° for 3 h and cooled. The resulting solid was crystallized from alcohol and dried under reduced pressure (75–80 mm), m.p. 198° (Found : C, 50.09; H, 3.75; N, 18.07. $C_{13}H_{12}N_4OCl_2$ requires : C, 50.18; H, 3.89; N, 18.01%).

Di(4-chlorophenyl)carbazone (3) : Compound 2 (0.015 mol) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (480 ml) and diluted with 1 N H_2SO_4 (160 ml) and 2 drops of ferric alum (10%) was added. Then a solution of potassium persulphate (0.036 mol) in water (160 ml) was added drop wise with vigorous stirring, allowed to stand for 30 min, diluted with ice-cold water and extracted with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with distilled water till it was free from acetic acid. On evaporation of ether the resulting product was obtained and it was chromatographed over SiO_2 (60–120 mesh). Eluted with acetone-chloroform mixture (20 : 80) and on evaporation of the eluent gave pale yellow crystals of 3 (58%), m.p. 102° (Found : C, 49.72; H, 3.15; N, 17.80. $C_{13}H_{10}N_4OCl_2$ requires : C, 50.50; H, 3.26; N, 18.12%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3385, 3240, 3070, 1700, 1580, 1495 and 755 cm^{-1} ; δ 1.60 (1H, s, NH), 6.3 (1H, s, OH), 6.7–7.5 (8H, m, ArH); m/z 310 (M^+).

The solution of the ligand was prepared in dioxan. All the metal ion solutions were prepared from their corresponding sulphates or nitrates (A.R., B.D.H.) in double-distilled water and were standardised by EDTA method⁸. Carbonate free sodium hydroxide solution was prepared by conventional method⁹ and it was standardized with potassium hydrogen phthalate. Sodium perchlorate (Riedel) was used to maintain constant ionic strength. Perchloric acid (70%, A.R.) was procured from s.d. fine Chemicals, Mumbai, India and it was standardized with sodium hydroxide solution. Dioxan (A.R.) was purified by the method used by Math *et al.*¹⁰. A solution of sodium hydroxide was used as the titrant. The titrations were carried out in an inert atmosphere by passing nitrogen gas, pre-saturated with 50% (v/v) aqueous dioxan before passing through the reaction mixture. The titrations were carried out in a specially designed double walled beaker.

The method of Calvin-Bjerrum as modified by Irving and Rossotti¹¹ was followed to determine the proton-ligand and metal-ligand stability constants.

The following sets of titrations were performed at three different temperatures, 25, 35 and 45 ± 0.1° in 50% dioxan-water medium : (i) 5 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO₄ (1.0 M) + 25 ml dioxan + 15 ml H₂O; (ii) 5 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO₄ (1.0 M) + 5 ml ligand (2.0 × 10⁻² M) + 20 ml dioxan + 15 ml H₂O; (iii) 5 ml HClO₄ (0.1 M) + 5 ml NaClO₄ (1.0 M) + 5 ml ligand (2.0 × 10⁻² M) + 5 ml metal ion solution (5 × 10⁻³ M) + 20 ml dioxan + 10 ml H₂O. Total volume in each case was 50 ml and ionic strength was maintained constant at 1.1 M with NaClO₄ and HClO₄. The ratio of the metal salt to reagent was maintained at nearly 1 : 4 in all the titrations in order to satisfy the maximum coordination possibility of the metal ions.

In all the calculations, pH correction and volume correction factors have been applied for dioxan-water mixture. From the titration curves of solutions (i) and (ii) the \bar{n}_A (average number of protons associated/ligand molecule) values were calculated at various pH values using the Irving-Rossotti relation. The pK_a values were determined by plotting \bar{n}_A vs pH, as well as from the intercepts of the linear plots of log [$\bar{n}_A/(1 - \bar{n}_A)$] vs pH. From the titration curves using the solution (i), (ii) and (iii), \bar{n} (metal-ligand formation number) values of the metal complexes were determined at various pH values.

From the pK_a and \bar{n}_A values at different pH values, the corresponding values of pL were calculated. The \bar{n} and pL data were subjected to the weighted least squares method developed by Sullivan *et al.*^{12(a)} on a PC-XT computer to get β_n values. The weighted least squares treatment determined the set of β_n values which make the function U .

$$U = \sum_{n=0}^N (y - x - nz)\beta_n x^n$$

nearest to zero, by minimizing S ,

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^I W_i U^2(x_i, y_i, z_i)$$

with respect to variation in β_n . S_{\min} has the same statistical distribution as χ^2 with K degrees of freedom and the weights defined in accordance with Rydberg and Sullivan^{12(b)}. S_{\min} can be equated to χ^2 . The stability constants thus calculated are given in Table 1. The ΔH° was calculated by the graphical method while ΔG° and ΔS° were calculated by conventional methods (Table 2).

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